

Bio-synthesized Hydroxyapatite Nanoparticles for Sensor and Antimicrobial applications

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Abstract

Hydroxyapatite ($\text{Ca}_{10}(\text{PO}_4)_6(\text{OH})_2$, HA) is the main mineral constituent of natural bone and teeth. It attracts considerable interest in many areas because of its acid-base properties, ion-exchange ability, biocompatibility and adsorption capacity. A great variety of cationic and anionic substitutions in HA is possible due to its “open structure” [1]. The characteristics of HA NPs depend on the method of synthesis which influences particle size, shapes and phase purity. A number of novel processing routes such as dry, wet, hydrothermal, sonochemical, and microwave assisted process have been developed for preparing HA powders [2]. Chemical method may successfully produce pure, well-defined nanoparticles, these are quite expensive and potentially dangerous to the environment. On the other hand, biosynthetic methods employing either biological microorganisms or plant extracts are simple and eco-friendly. Here we report to synthesis HA Nps by using different plant extract such as Eucalyptus, Ocimum basicilium, Plectranthus amboinicus, and Jusiticia adathoda by microwave method. Biosynthesized HA Nps were successfully applied to fabrication of sensor and antimicrobial application. The Electrochemical behavior of 2-Nitrophenol was investigated by cyclic voltammetry (CV), differential pulse voltammetry (DPV) techniques by using pristine HA and plant extracts assisted HA Nps modified GCE. Among them, Plectranthus Amboincus assisted HA Nps modified GCE exhibits excellent electro catalytic activity towards 2-Nitrophenol. Moreover, it has been good sensitive for determination of 2-Nitrophenol over a wide linear range from 0.2 μM to 60 μM with the lowest limit of detection 90nM. The nanoparticles samples were evaluated against *S. aureus*, *S. mutants*, *P. aeruginosa* and *E. coli* species. The inhibition of zone for bacterial species most significant effect of tested range from 13 to 21mm of *S. mutants*, and *E. coli* 11 to 17mm. The highest inhibition of zone was observed in gram-positive bacteria, due to the van der Waals interaction (electrostatic interaction) between accessible negatively charged bacterial cell membrane and positively charged nanoparticles.

Keywords: *Hydroxyapatite nanoparticles; Plectranthus amboinicus; Sensors; Antimicrobial activity;*

References

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